

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

“GREEN OXIDIZER” - N₂O IN THE REACTION OF COHERENTLY SYNCHRONIZED GAS-PHASE OXIDATION OF 3 - METHYLPYRIDINE

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*“Coherent Synchronized Oxidation Reaction by Hydrogen Peroxide”, Amsterdam: “Elsevier” 2007. p. 325
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Abstract

The results of studies of coherently synchronized reactions of the decomposition of nitrous oxide and the oxidation of 3-methylpyridine in the gas phase are presented. The optimal conditions for obtaining the target products in this reaction have been identified. The influence of process parameters on the yield of reaction products is shown. Areas of selective oxidation of 3-methylpyridine were identified and optimal conditions for obtaining the target products were determined.

Keywords: 3-methylpyridine, coherent-synchronized, dehydrodimerization, 3,3-ethylenedipyridine and 2,2-dipyridyl-3,3-dimethyl

Currently, the economic need for nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds prompts the search for new effective technologies for their production. Known technologies for the synthesis of pyridine bases are not efficient enough and have a number of disadvantages associated with the deactivation of catalysts, the use of diluents, polymerization inhibitors and reduced pressure, which complicates the process. It should be added that pyridine and its derivatives are of particular interest, i.e. containing in addition to a carbon atom and a nitrogen atom. This gives these compounds a number of special properties. These properties include various types of fungicidal, pharmacological activity; one of the common drugs is paraquat, which is produced as a herbicide for weed control. In addition, there are special forms of pyridine bases (dipyridyls), which form a stable complex with a number of metals (in particular, the ruthenic complex, which catalyzes the photodecomposition of water into hydrogen and oxygen, etc., is being widely studied).

Therefore, the synthesis of pyridine bases and their derivatives by fairly simple transformations, for example, dehydrogenation of the corresponding higher saturated compounds, is relevant. From this point of view, the synthesis of important pyridine bases using nitrous oxide without the use of catalysts is of theoretical and applied interest, since the reactions proceed using a simplified technology. The advantage of coherently synchronized reactions of oxidation of pyridine

and its derivatives with nitrous oxide is that the process occurs at atmospheric pressure, without the use of catalysts, with a relatively high yield of the target product and high selectivity.

In recent decades, nitrous oxide has attracted increasing attention from researchers as a selective oxygen donor for the catalytic oxidation of hydrocarbons. It is particularly widely used in gas-phase oxidation of hydrocarbons.

In works [1-5], nitrous oxide is used as a selective oxidizing agent to carry out the transformations of pyridine bases.

The authors of [6] studied linear alkenes and since the oxidation of alkenes with nitrous oxide occurs in the liquid phase, it seems important to assess the solubility of nitrous oxide in some alkenes and organic solvents. Unlike symmetrical ethylene, for propylene, where the carbon atoms at the double bond are not equivalent, the reaction leads to the formation of two isomeric carbonyl compounds - propanal (23%) and acetone (31%).

In [7], it was found that due to the symmetrical arrangement of the double bond in the unsubstituted rings of carbocyclic alkenes, their oxidation can be ensured by a single ketone, which in all cases is formed with high selectivity (94-99%). A weak tendency of influence from the reaction in series of cyclopentene to cyclododecene, which due to the opening rings leads to the formation of aldehydes. The reaction mixture produces the expected two isomeric cyclic ketones with

overall selectivities of 95 and 97%, respectively, and a small amount of aldol condensation products is detected.

In this work [8], the oxidation of cycloalkadienes such as 1,4-cyclohexadiene and 1,5-cyclooctadiene, which have isolated double bonds and 1,3-cyclohexadiene with conjugated bonds, was studied. In the oxidation of 1,4-cyclohexadiene, 3- and 2-cyclohexen-1-ones were obtained as the main reaction products in yields of 90-92%, respectively.

The authors of [9] found that during the oxidation of 1,2-dihydro-naphthalene, the reaction proceeds with the formation of α - and β -tetralones with a high total selectivity of 93%. Oxygen is preferentially added to the α -position. As a result, the amount of α -tetralone is approximately twice that of β -tetralone.

In [10], the oxidation of five-membered heterocyclic alkenes with nitrous oxide was studied and as a result of the work it was found that the oxygen-containing ring of 2,5DHF is oxidized with a ketone yield of 94%, while rings containing nitrogen and sulfur indicate a strong tendency for side reactions to occur.

Thus, the reaction of liquid-phase oxidation with nitrous oxide involves alkenes of different types: aliphatic, cyclic, bicyclic, heterocyclic alkenes and their derivatives, as well as dienes.

In this aspect, of significant theoretical and applied interest, undoubtedly, is the synthesis of practically important pyridine bases using nitrous oxide with-

out the participation of catalysts, and to activate the latter, organic acids and their anhydrides and other activators are not used, complete disposal of which and the products of their decomposition, would pose certain difficulties.

In connection with the above, we experimentally studied the oxidation reaction of 3-methylpyridine with nitrous oxide in the gas phase, without the use of catalysts, at atmospheric pressure. The work shows how practically important compounds can be obtained with high selectivity by oxidizing 3-methylpyridine with the "green oxidizer" – N_2O .

Experimental part

Experiments were carried out to study the kinetics of homogeneous oxidation of 3-methylpyridine (3-MP) with the participation of nitrous oxide. The experimental setup and methodology used to study coupled oxidation with nitrous oxide are described in detail in [11,12]. The design of the reactor ensures that nitrous oxide is introduced into the reaction zone through a quartz tube in an undecomposed form. Through another quartz tube, i.e. Separately from nitrous oxide, the initial oxidizable substance, preheated in a gaseous state, is fed into the reactor. The hardening zone, which follows the reaction zone, is located as close as possible to it. This hardening system is used to prevent the development of oxidation of reaction products outside the reaction zone. Qualitative and quantitative determination of reaction products was carried out by gas chromatomass-spectroscopy.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1. Dependence of the yield of reaction products on temperature.

1 – 3,3-ethylenedipyridine,
2 – 2,2-dipyridyl 3,3-dimethyl.

Feed rates: 3-MP=1,2ml/h, N_2O =100ml/h.

Experimental studies of the oxidation reaction of 3-MP with nitrous oxide were carried out in the temperature range of 580-610°C. As a result of research, it was found that an increase in temperature from 580 to 610°C is accompanied by an increase in the yield of

3,3-ethylenedipyridine and 2,2-dipyridyl 3,3-dimethyl (Fig. 1, curves 1,2), this is due to an increase in the rate of generation of highly active atomic oxygen centers during the thermal decomposition of nitric oxide (1). The feed rates of 3-MP and N_2O remained constant.

Fig.2. Dependence of the yield of reaction products on the feed rate of 3-MP. 1 - 3,3-ethylenedipyrindine, 2 - 2,2-dipyridil 3,3-dimethyl.

T= 610°C, feed rate N₂O = 100ml/h

A subsequent increase in temperature (above 610°C) leads to an increase in the amount of by-products. The flow rate of 3-MP was studied in the range of 0.4-2.0 ml/h (temperature 610°C, the flow rate of nitric oxide (1) remained unchanged - 100 ml/s). As a result

of the studies, it was found that in this range, the dehydrodimerization reaction of 3-MP with nitrogen oxide (1) mainly occurs to produce 3,3-ethylenedipyrindine and 2,2-dipyridyl-3,3-dimethyl (Fig. 2, curve 1 ,2).

Fig.3. Dependence of the yield of reaction products on the feed rate N₂O.

1 - 3,3-ethylenedipyrindine,
2 - 2,2-dipyridil 3,3-dimethyl.

T=610°C , feed rates 3-MP= 1,2ml/h.

Further experimental studies are related to the rate of nitric oxide supply (1). The supply rate of nitric oxide (1) was studied in the range of 50-200 ml/h (temperature 610°C, 3-MP supply rate = 1.2 ml/h remained unchanged). As can be seen from Figure 3, at a supply rate of nitric oxide (1) of 100 ml/s, the yield of 3,3-ethylenedipyrindine is 26.8 wt.% (Fig. 3, curve 1). The yield of 2,2-dipyridyl-3,3-dimethyl is 28.9 wt.% (Fig. 3, curve 2). The yields of 3,3-ethylenedipyrindine and 2,2-dipyridyl-3,3-dimethyl increased as the nitric oxide

delivery rate increased from 50 ml/h to 100 ml/h. After increasing the rate of delivery of nitric oxide (1) (100-200 ml/h), the yields of 3,3-ethylenedipyrindine and 2,2-dipyridyl-3,3-dimethyl decrease. This is due to changes in the contact time of the reagents.

The reaction products revealed the formation of a by-product - 3,3-methylenedipyrindine up to 0.8 wt.% (Scheme 1). Qualitative and quantitative determination of reaction products was carried out by gas chromatomass-spectroscopy (Agilent Technologies 7820A).

Schemt 1

Conclusion

Thus, dehydrodimerization of 3-MP with the “green oxidizer” nitrogen oxide (1) in the gas phase at a temperature of 610°C leads mainly to the production of practically important products - 3,3-ethylenedipyridine and 2,2-dipyridyl-3,3-dimethyl, yield which respectively amounts to 26.8 wt.% and 28.9 wt.%, with relatively high selectivity.

These studies show how, in the mode of coherent synchronization of the thermal decomposition of nitrogen oxide (1) and dehydrodimerization of 3-MP, precursors necessary in the chemical, pharmaceutical, and petrochemical industries were obtained.

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